

RELEVANCE OF ETHICAL VISION TOWARDS HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Through this study an attempt is being taken to discuss as how the ethical vision can play a relevant role to make human resource management successful. With a view to systematizing the discussion on the topic referred to here, the entire study is divided into three parts. The first part entitled “Theoretical Approach” includes an introduction, meaning of ethics and business ethics and objective of the study. The second part entitled “Relevance of Ethical vision towards HRM” provides a comprehensive study, where a detail discussion is done as how ethical thoughts and vision can be successfully mixed in formulating human resource polices as well as implementing these polices in practices to make the Human Resource Management effective. In doing so, all possible aspects of human resource management are reviewed from ethical point of view. The third part “conclusion” gives some recommendation by virtue of which the top management can create an ethical climate for human resource management system in an organization.

Key Words: Ethical Vision, Human Resource Management, Business Ethics

Theoretical Approach

1.1 Introduction

Human aspects and human relations are applicable anywhere and in any department. Hence individual behaviour, group behaviour, personality, attitudes, perception, conflicts, leadership are some of the factors which have to be taken into account to evaluate fair-unfair, good-bad or ethical-unethical behaviour. This subject of evaluation should also take care of situation, the organisational work culture, compulsions, expectations and peer pressure. Employees have feelings, likes, dislikes, joys-sorrows, emotions and the behavioural pattern tend to change with experience. Higher the experience level better will be the work ethics. It is the newer and less experience employees, who need to be trained, groomed and shaped for work effectiveness and ethical values. In order to survive in the competitive world the employees resort to various fair and unfair means. Those who adopt fair means achieve slow growth. Employees following unfair methods are likely to grow faster or lose the joy, which means they are taking known risk in chase of greed, human Resource Managers deal with human resources within the organisation and are mostly concerned with human values. They must work consciously to develop organisational value. The value system must be based on the philosophy that men must be believed in and trusted. It is only then that they would give their best to the company. Organisational values are shaped by the individual values of leaders. Values provide a common language for aligning a company’s leadership and its people. That is

why, there are a lot of relevant aspects for the formulating and practices of Human Resource policies based on ethical vision

1.2 Meaning of Ethics and Business Ethics

The concept of ethics comes from the Greek word “ethos that means both an individual’s character and a community’s culture. Generally it is believed that business ethics involves adhering to legal regulatory, professional and company standard, keeping promises and commitments and abiding by general principles like fairness, froth, honesty and respect. “The Institute of Global Ethics defines ethics as “obedience to the unenforceable.1 “Business ethics is the study and of business situations, activities and decisions where issues of right and wrong are address.”2

The famous missionary physician and humanitarian Albert Schweitzer defined ethics as “our concern for good behavior. We feel an obligation to consider not only own personal well being, but also that of other human beings. This meaning is similar to the precept of the Golden Rule : Do unto others as you would have then do unto you. In business, ethics can be defined as the capacity to reflect on values in the corporate decision making process, to determine how these values and decision affect various stakeholder groups and to establish how managers can use these observations in day to day company management.3

1.3 Objective of the study

The basic objective of the study is to examine the relevance of ethical vision in designing human resource policies and accordingly to examine the ethical values in implementing these polices in practices to make the management of human resource successful. In doing so, the study aims at discussing various relevant dimensions of human resource management, which includes selection, promotion, transfer, performance appraisal & training.

Relevance of ethical vision towards HRM.

According to the objectives mentioned above, in this part, the following HR functions are reviewed from ethical point of view.

2.1 Selection: - Selection is one of the important functions of Human Resource Management. The human resource managers should take all necessary care to make the selection process scientifically, honestly and objectively. No subjective factor ought to be allowed to influence the selection. In USA, the employer declares equal employment opportunities. But in India, equal employment opportunities are not practised. In the public sector, percentage of jobs are kept reserved. for scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and OBC candidate.4 In selection false claim of age, qualification and experience, forge marks cards to claim certain qualification etc. are some unethical and unfair kind of behaviour generally found from employee or candidate. Moreover, from employer side also, biased attitude in selection, giving different treatments and facilities to different candidate, not behaving respectfully with union leader are some unethical practices seen in selection process. These types of unethical practices stand on the way of performing activities of human resource management in proper way. “The simplest way to turn up an organisation, ethically speaking, is to hire more ethical peole.”5 This can start before the applicant event applies, by creating recruitment materials with explicit reference to the organizations emphasis on ethics.

“Employers can then use tools such as honesty test and meticulous background checks to screen out undesirable.6 Moreover the human resource managers should ask some behavioural questions such as “Have you

ever observed someone stretching the rules at work? What did you do about it? And “Have you even had to go against company guidelines and procedures in order to get something done.”⁷ Hence, the apparent fairness of the selection process is important.

2.2 Promotion: - Promotion should be made on the basis of seniority or merit or seniority-cum-merit basis. There should be no favouritism in promotion. If any favouritism is done, employees will be demoralised and feel frustrated and trade union activities will increase as a result of unethical activities of the management. Industrial peace will be disturbed. “Women and ethnic minorities are severely under-represented on boards of directors. For instance, in the UK, the average board consists of 8.7 white members and 0.2 minority members, whilst minorities occupy only 1.7% of directorships in Canada despite representing over 16% of the population.”⁸ The fact that senior management positions in virtually all industries in Europe and North America are dominated by white males might also be tackled by specific leadership training for women and minorities once they are already within the organization. For example, “The German automotive company Volkswagen AG operates a ‘Women Driving Award’, which awards achievement of women engineers in the company and is specifically designed to encourage career advancement of women in a profession that is still largely male dominated”⁹

2.3 Transfer :

A consistent policy should be followed in cases of transfers. They should not be used as a penal measure. Frequent transfer is very inconvenient for employees because it disturbs their family life.

2.4 Performance appraisal:

Performance appraisals are uniquely personal and important matter to most employees, and employees therefore enter the appraisal interview with a heightened sensitivity regarding fair treatment. To most employees, unfairness here reflects not just the supervisor’s actions, but also the employer’s inaction, in having not taken the necessary steps to prevent the unjust treatment.

How the supervisor do the appraisals is important. “Studies and practical experience confirm that, in practice, some manager ignore accuracy and honesty in performance appraisals and instead use the process for political purpose such as encouraging employees with whom they don’t get along to leave the firm.”¹⁰

Human resource manager should maintain fairness and some essential ethical standards in handling performance appraisal procedure and these standards should be clearly disclosed to the employees. So that employees are able to understand the basis upon which they are going to be appraised and the appraisal themselves should be performed objectively and fairly.

2.5 Training: Ethics training to employees is immensely important to make the human resource management ethically sound and effective. Ethics training usually includes showing employees how to recognize ethical dilemmas, how to use ethical framework (such as codes of conduct) to resolve problems, and how to use human resource activities in ethical way. “Managers are given training in some companies like General Dynamics, McDonnell Douglas in USA. Even the supervisor as well as other who are likely to encounter an ethical question at work is provided with training.”¹¹ The training programmes acquaint employees with :

* Official company policy on ethical issues; how such policies can be translated into the specifics of very day decision making.

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- * Simulated case studies based on actual events in the company used to illustrate how to apply ethical principles on the job problems of everyday.
- * Arrange Workshop for employees frequently and to make aware of company commitment to ethics. These workshop may be for half days and are arranged by line managers.

Thus concerted and systematic attention to ethics will reduce and eliminate such risks. Carefully designed and administered ethics training programmes can bring positive contribution to the company.

Robber Kreitner has specified key features of effective training programmes.

- * Top management support
- * Open discussion on resolving of realistic case / dilemmas
- * A clear focus identification on ethical theme in all training.
- * A mechanism for anonymously reporting ethical violations.
- * An organization climate that rewards ethical conduct.
- * Provide all staff with a copy of code of ethics and also code of conduct. Also explain all employees the working of the same with their role.¹²

2.6 : Others-

Moreover, top management should see that there is no sexual harassment of female employees at the place of work. Sexual harassment is punishable under the Indian Penal Code “ All over the world government have made rules to protect women against sexual violationsIn India only in teaching professions the women participation is quite good and upto 40%. In all other working areas it does not exceed 20% In India the proportion of women employees is increasing since last 10-15 years due to growth in ITES and BPO sector. The women employee’s percentage in these large scale companies is around 30% Moreover, in BPO companies, the work house are mostly sunset to sunrise that is throughout the night. Such situation and more numbers have given ample scope to indulge in willing and unwilling sexual relations. There are more and more cases of sexual harassments in MNCs.... these companies have slowly changing the socio - cultural values of India.”¹³ In spite of these sexual harassment In Indian conditions, women do not complain to employer or go to courts due to fear of creating ill- reputation for self. Most of the cases get hushed up untold. Very few cases are facing enquiry in office or go to court. Even in courts the case gets delayed and it is difficult to prove the harassment due to proofs, witness problems. Hence law is not as effective as it should be to punish the offenders and discourage such incidents. In this salvation, the top management should remember the ethics of Gandhi philosophy. “Gandhi made no distinction between man and woman. All were equal in his eyes.....Gandhiji held that woman’s grace lay in her character and her modesty. He did not want her to be a plaything for man. Woman must cease to consider herself the object of man’s lust. She must refuse to adorn herself for men including her husband, if she was to be an equal partner with man” ¹⁴ In addition to above, Unfair labor practices, unsafe workplace, bad working Conditions, long working hours, house, no redressal of ILO grievances and non-implementation of ILO convention etc are other unethical practices frequently found in case of Human Resource management

Conclusion

Human Resource Management should treat employees as humanity, always as an end and never as a means only. Human are constituted as an important resource and in most cases, it is the most costly resource as well. Human beings should deserve respect and on the other side should be entitled to certain basic rights. So the central

ethical issues in HRM should be framed around the issue of rights and duties of employees. It should stress that these rights are all more or less directly deduced from the general notion of human rights and most of them are in some way or other codified in various acts and laws. The codification of worker's rights should be advanced, so that corporations in most cases should simply have to obey the existing law in the country. Managing human resource often requires making decisions in which fairness plays a role. If the human resource manager hire on candidate and reject another, promote one and demote another, pay one more and one less, and settle one's grievances while rejecting another's, then how employees react to these decisions depends, to some extent, on whether they think the decisions and the processes that led up to them were fair. Fairness is inseparable from what most people think of as "justice". A company that is just is among other things, equitable, fair, impartial and unbiased in how it does things. With respect to employee relations, experts generally define organizational justice in terms of its components – Distributive justice, procedural justice, and interpersonal or inter active justice.

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